

Development and Characterisation of Aluminium Metal Matrix Composites with SiC Reinforcement

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Abstract: Metal Matrix Composites (MMCs) have evoked a keen interest in recent times for potential applications in aerospace and automotive industries owing to their superior strength to weight ratio and high temperature resistance. In the present study a modest attempt has been made to develop aluminium based silicon carbide particulate MMCs with an objective to develop a conventional low cost method of producing MMCs. Aluminium and SiC (220 mesh) has been chosen as matrix and reinforcement material respectively. Different weight fractions such as 5%, 10%, 15% of SiC were considered for making MMC specimen. Experiment has been conducted on different weight fractions of reinforcement material to study the Characterization of SiC Particulate Reinforced Aluminium Matrix Composite. Mechanical Properties of MMC were tested. Then the specimen also characterized with the help of Microstructure study.

Keywords: Metal Matrix Composites MMC's, Silicon Carbide SiC, AA-6063

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last thirty years composite materials, plastics and ceramics have been the dominant emerging materials. The volume and number of applications of composite materials have grown steadily, penetrating and conquering new markets relentlessly. While composites have already proven their worth as weight saving materials, the current challenge is to make them cost effective.

A composite material is a material composed of two or more distinct phases (matrix phase and reinforcing phase) and having bulk properties significantly different from those of any of the constituents. And composite material is composed of reinforcement (fibers, particles, flakes, and/or fillers) embedded in a matrix (polymers, metals, ceramics). The matrix holds the reinforcement to form the desired shape while the reinforcement improves the overall mechanical properties of the matrix. When designed properly, the new combined material exhibits better strength than each individual material. Many common materials (metals, alloys, doped ceramics and polymers mixed with additives) also have a small number of dispersed phases in their structures, however they are not considered as composite materials since their properties are similar to those of their base constituents (physical property of steel are similar to those of pure iron). Favorable properties of composites materials are high stiffness and high strength, low density, high temperature stability, high electrical and thermal conductivity, adjustable coefficient of thermal expansion, corrosion resistance, improved wear resistance etc.

II. OBJECTIVE

The main objective of this paper is to fabricate a metal matrix composite specimen, which is made up of

Aluminium metal matrix with reinforcement material as silicon carbide powder particles. The characterization study of pure Aluminium and the particulate reinforced composite have been studied. The primary goal of this paper is to develop a mechanics-based experimental approach to estimate the characteristic study of Aluminium metal matrix composites. The specific objectives are,

1. To synthesis particle reinforced aluminum metal matrix composite using liquid state processing.
2. To study the effect of weight percentage on mechanical behavior of aluminum metal matrix composite.
3. To characterize the properties of aluminum metal matrix composite.

III. METHODOLOGY

Here the process is carried out with the help of open hearth furnace. The fabrication method of composites and the selected materials are detailed below.

IV. MATERIALS:

- The matrix aluminium is chosen as **AA-6063**. Its chemical composition is shown in the table 4.1 below, (in weight percentage).
- The **Silicon carbide particles** were considered as reinforcement for making MMC. (the particle size is 220 mesh).

TABLE.4.1
CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF MATRIX ALUMINIUM.

Material	Al	Si	Mg	Others
%	98.649	0.536	0.55	0.265

4.1. FABRICATION OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE

In general, there are many types of furnaces such as; Oil fired furnace, Muffle furnace, Open hearth furnace, Induction furnace. In this project, the Al/SiC metal matrix composite was prepared with the help of open-hearth furnace. All the melting was carried out in a graphite crucible in an open-hearth furnace. The reinforcement particles were preheated at 1100°C to loosen the grain boundaries and to remove any moisture contents present in it. The furnace temperature was first raised above the liquidus to melt the matrix completely and was then cooled down just below the liquidus to keep in a semi-solid state.

At this stage the preheated reinforcement particles were added, and automatic mechanical mixing was carried out for about 5-6 minutes at a normal stirring rate of 500 rpm. After sufficient mixing was done, the

composite slurry was reheated to a just liquid state. In the final mixing process, the temperature was controlled within $760 \pm 100^{\circ}\text{C}$. Pouring of the composite slurry was carried out in the die mould prepared according to the specifications of test specimens.

Fig 4.1 Block diagram of MMC Manufacturing

V. TESTING

The entire specimens were made according to the procedure that was mentioned in the Methodology. The composites of Aluminum with Silicon Carbide were made and characterized.

Characterization of Al/Sic Composite:

The attractive physical and mechanical properties that can be obtained with metal matrix composites, such as high specific modulus, strength and thermal stability. The various factors controlling the properties of particulate MMCs and influence of the manufacturing route on the MMC properties has also been reviewed by several investigators. Improvement in modulus, strength, fatigue, creep and wear resistance has already been demonstrated for a variety of reinforcements of these properties; the tensile strength is the most convenient and widely quoted measurement and is of central importance in many applications. The strength of particle-reinforced composites is observed to be most strongly dependent on the volume fraction and

particle size of the reinforcement. Dislocation strengthening will play a more significant role in the MMC than in the unreinforced alloy due to the increased dislocation density.

5.1 IMPACT TEST:

The Impact test specimen was prepared (Fig 5.1a, b, c) according to ASTM 256-05 with various weight fractions. The dimensions are length 65mm, width 13mm and thickness 4mm can be found at ASTM 256-05. The test of the specimen was carried out with the help of the Impact test (Charpy) at room temperature.

Fig.5.1a. Impact test specimen at 5% weight fractions of SiC.

Fig 5.1b. Impact test specimen at 10% weight fractions of SiC.

Fig 5.1c. Impact test specimen at 15% weight fractions of SiC.

5.2 TENSILE TEST

The Tensile test specimen was prepared (Fig 5.2a, b, c) according to ASTM 638-05 with various weight fractions.

Fig 5.2a. Tensile test specimen at 5% weight fractions of SiC.

Fig 5.2b. Tensile test specimen at 10% weight fractions of SiC.

Fig 5.2c. Tensile test specimen at 15% weight fractions of SiC.

As per ASTM 638-05, the dimensions are 225mm in length, 20mm in diameter and 50mm in gauge length. The test of the specimen was carried out with the help of the computerized universal testing Machine.

5.2 HARDNESS TEST:

The hardness of the samples was measured using a rockwell hardness measuring machine. Hardness test has been conducted on each specimen using a load of 150 N and a steel ball of diameter 5 mm, The scale was used are C- scale. The load was applied for 30 seconds. In order to eliminate possible segregation effect a minimum four hardness readings were taken for each specimen at different location of the test samples.

5.3 MICROSTRUCTURE TEST:

The most important aspects of the microstructure are the distribution of the reinforcing particles, and this depends on the processing and fabrication routes involved. The oxides of reinforcing particles used in the composites have a varying density. Density of the particles is one of the important factors determining the distribution of the particles in molten metal. Particles having higher density than molten metal can settle at the bottom of the bath slowly and particles of lower density can segregate at the top. During subsequent pouring of the composite melt, the particle content may vary from one casting to another or even it can vary in the same casting from one region to another. Therefore uniform distribution of the particles in the melt is a necessary condition for uniform distribution of the particles in the castings. The properties of composites are finally dependent on the distribution of the particles. The microstructure was observed using optical microscope of model OLYMPUS GX-51, using the lense of 20X, The microstructure was magnified under 1 micrometer. Micro structural characterization studies were conducted on reinforced samples; the studies were conducted on the as-processed and machined composite castings in order to investigate the distribution of Silicon carbide particles retained in the metal matrix. The specimens were mechanically polished using standard metallographic practices and etched.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6.1 IMPACT TEST:

The Impact strength of Silicon carbide reinforced Aluminium Metal Matrix composite is shown in Fig 6.1. The Impact test results depict that the Impact strength of 0%, 5%, 10% and 15% weight fractions of SiC reinforcements are 19.4, 22.56, 23.4, 25.1 N-m respectively. Compared to the above results the maximum results were obtained in 15% weight fraction of SiC. It is identified that Impact strength of the composites increases gradually from increasing of Silicon Carbide.

Fig 6.1 Impact Strength at various weight fractions of SiC

6.2 TENSILE TEST:

The Tensile strength of Silicon carbide reinforced Aluminium Metal Matrix composite is shown in Fig 6.2. The test results depict that the Tensile strength of 0%, 5%, 10% and 15% weight fractions of SiC reinforcements are 100, 171, 210, 297 MPa respectively. Compared to the above results the maximum strength was obtained in 15% weight fraction of SiC. It is identified that tensile strength of the composites increases gradually by increasing of Silicon Carbide.

Fig 6.2 Tensile Strength at various fractions of SiC

6.3 HARDNESS TEST

Fig 6.3a Hardness at various weight fractions of SiC

The Hardness values of Silicon carbide reinforced Aluminium Metal Matrix composite is shown in Fig 6.3a. The test results depict that the Hardness values of 0%, 5%, 10% and 15% weight fractions of SiC reinforcements are 38, 49, 51.66, 54.33 respectively. Compared to the above results the maximum value was obtained in 15% weight fraction of SiC. It is identified that Hardness of the composites increases gradually by increasing of Silicon Carbide.

Fig 6.3b Hardness values of tested tensile specimens

The Hardness values of the tensile specimen after testing are in Fig 6.3b. The test results depict that the Hardness values of 0%, 5%, 10% and 15% weight fractions of SiC of the tested tensile specimens are 35.8, 43.6, 45.8, 52.2 respectively. Compared to the above results the maximum value was obtained in 15% weight fraction of SiC.

6.4 MICROSTRUCTURE TEST:

Microstructure which is obtained from the optical microscope reveals that, near uniform distribution of Silicon Carbide particles were obtained. The microstructure also shows that there is good interfacial bonding between reinforcement particles and aluminium matrix material. The microstructure reveals that there are no voids or discontinuities and a slight micro-segregation of particles in some places. The distribution of SiC particles is influenced by the tendency of particles to float due to density differences and interactions with the solidifying metal. The following figures (6.4a, 6.4b, 6.4c) shows that the microstructures of the specimen made up of 5%, 10%, 15 % weight fractions of SiC.

Fig 6.4a Structure of 5% of weight fractions of SiC.

Fig 6.4b Structure of 10% of weight fractions of SiC.

Fig 6.4c Structure of 15% of weight fractions of SiC.

Thus here we are adding up SiC particles with an increase of an amount 5% in each of the three stages. It is evident that there is a strong interfacial bond existing in between this additive and the base matrix material. Here, Aluminium matrix. In each step, while we gradually increase the amount of SiC particles, it is obvious that the hardness increases in a direct proportion to the percentage of SiC by weight. This is evident from the photographs of the microstructure given above. The bar graph depicts this gradual change in each step. There are two significant reasons which determine the scattering or distribution of particles in

the matrix. The first one is the natural tendency of the additive particles to lay floated above the mixture due to density difference and the other is the interaction between the solidifying material. The maximum result of hardness is obtained in the third step, while we added 15% of SiC particles.

VII. CONCLUSION

A metal matrix composite specimen is produced with the help of aluminium as matrix material and SiC as reinforcement material. The MMC was produced with varying weight fraction such as 5%, 10%, 15% of reinforcement. Many trials were made, and the specimen is produced accordingly. The composite material which is developed is then machined, characterized. Micro structure characterization also studied in the specimens with the help of Optical Microscope.

The existing composite materials, compared to the matrix, have shown better physical, mechanical and properties at room temperature. Performance benefits of using the Al MMCs in automotive industry are reduced weight and improved wear resistance, together with better thermal conductivity comparing to the traditional materials. In the future, applications of Al MMCs are likely to continue to grow because of the continuing pressures to reduce vehicle weight and levels of vehicle emissions and to increase fuel economy. The following conclusions were made,

- Aluminium matrix composite containing 5%, 10%, 15% weight fractions of Silicon carbide particles were synthesized successfully by using liquid state processing.
- The Impact test of composite reveals that the SiC reinforced composite shows better results were achieved in the form of increasing of SiC.
- The Tensile test of composite reveals that the SiC reinforced composite shows better results were achieved in the form of increasing of SiC.
- The hardness results also show that the better hardness values were achieved in increasing of Reinforcement, and also the hardness values of fractured portion of the tested tensile specimens of various weight fractions are more than normal hardness specimens.
- Microstructure revealed near uniform distribution of Silicon carbide particles in the castings. The microstructure also revealed good interfacial bond between matrix and particles.

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